

INFLUENCE OF INTRA-YARN PERMEABILITY ON MESO-SCALE PERMEABILITY OF PLAIN WEAVE AND 3D FABRICS

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Introduction:

- An understanding of mesoscale permeability of complex porous preforms is of particular interest to achieve efficient and cost-effective resin impregnation of liquid composite moulding (LCM) [1,2]
- Typically, the preform consists of an arrangement of yarns with spacing in the order of *mm* wherein each yarn consists of thousands of filaments with spacing in the order of μm . (Figure 1)
- The fluid flow during infusion exchanges the mass between the intra and inter-yarn channels, meaning there is no dead-end of flow between the mesopores in the inter-yarn space and the micropore in the yarn [3].

Figure 1: 3D woven preform with binder yarn (from Optimise project University of Manchester, UK)

Objective:

- Identify the influence of intra-yarn permeability on the mesoscale permeability with weft, warp yarn spacing on the plain weave and 3D weave with binder yarn
- Pareto-optimal pattern of 3D weave fabric varying warp, weft, and binder spacing, pattern and number of layers using multi-objective optimisation Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA)-II [4].

Modeling methodology:

$$\text{Darcy's law } \frac{m}{\rho} = \frac{k}{\mu} \frac{P_1 - P_2}{L}$$

m Mass flow rate *P*₁ Inlet pressure
ρ Resin density *P*₂ Outlet pressure
μ Resin viscosity *L* Unit cell length
k Preform permeability

Generate 3D preform with optimisation parameters:

- Four types of pattern
- Binder yarn weight
- Spacing of warp yarn
- Spacing of weft yarn
- Number of layers [1:6]

Optimisation of NSGA II

- max_num_iteration: 30
- population_size: 50
- mutation_probability: 0.1
- elite_ratio: 0.01
- crossover_probability: 0.5
- parents_portion: 0.3
- crossover_type: uniform

Figure 2: Flow-chart of the preform optimisation

Results:

Table 1. Mesoscale permeability of an orthogonal weave

Preform type	Permeability [m ²]	Solid yarn	Porous yarn porosity (ϕ)	
2x2 warp symmetric weave Periodic Y BC and Z wall	K _{xx} / 10 ⁻¹⁰	3.7051	3.7790 ($\phi = 0.22$)	
			3.7790 ($\phi = 0.12$)	
3D preform (2warp, 3weft, 1binder) Periodic Y BC and Z wall	K _{xx} / 10 ⁻¹⁰	6.66	8.70 ($\phi = 0.22$)	
			K _{yy} / 10 ⁻¹⁰	9.99
			K _{zz} / 10 ⁻¹⁰	2.94
			10.02 ($\phi = 0.22$)	
			10.01 ($\phi = 0.12$)	
			2.68 ($\phi = 0.22$)	
			2.67 ($\phi = 0.12$)	

Figure 3: (a) Pareto-optimal generation of in-plane permeability K_{xx} with V_f considering porous yarn and (b) K_{yy} vs V_f with warp spacing using porous yarn.

Conclusions:

- Meso-scale permeability predictions based on porous yarns differed from solid yarns by up to 20%.
- Pareto-optimal design space of warp, weft and binder follows the Kozeny-Carman model.
- K_{yy} increases as the spacing between warp yarn decreases.
- It is necessary to incorporate the permeability of porous yarn in meso-scale permeability prediction.

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